

«ÚZLIKSIZ BILIMLENDIRIW SISTEMASÍDA ARALÍQTAN OQÍTÍWDÍN INTEGRACIYASÍ»

atamasındaǵı IV Xalıqaralıq ilimiy-teoriyalıq konferenciya

HOW TO NURTURE SCHOOL CHILDREN'S CREATIVITY IN THE CLASSROOM

Dilnoza Turdibekova,

*Phd student at TIAME National Research
University*

Email: dilnoza.muxtorova@gmail.com

Annotation: *A study examines how second-grade instructors assess creativity in order to gain a better understanding of how creativity can be developed in general education classrooms, as well as identify barriers to nurturing creativity.*

Key words: *creativity, literature review, classroom, schoolchildren, connection*

As the third millennium has progressed, creativity has become more prominent. Creativity in the classroom has a large role to play in 21st century education. A study examines how second-grade instructors assess creativity in order to gain a better understanding of how creativity can be developed in general education classrooms, as well as identify barriers to nurturing creativity. (S.Austin) The article summarizes the research on classroom creativity. Based on the disparities that were identified, teachers' approaches to encouraging creativity varied. Despite the fact that all survey respondents said they valued creativity, not all of them explicitly promoted that trait in their teaching.

There were two public elementary schools involved in the study, both with second grade teachers. These schools followed Louisiana State Standards. Researchers observed eight second grade classrooms during the study. As a result of convenience sampling and geographical proximity, a single second grade teacher participant was selected from a large pool of potential participants; purposive sampling took place, including criteria such as years of experience teaching second grade, reflecting the diversity of second grade teachers. Using qualitative data analysis, they employed educational criticism while following educational connoisseurship, since criticism gives connoisseurship a public face. Through the five lenses of educational connoisseurship, they categorize barriers, beliefs, and evidence in relation to the research issues. Qualitative research's flexibility allowed the study to follow the flow of discoveries since factors at the outset were unknown. Study findings revealed that teachers had little understanding of creativity and the creative process. There was a lack of uniform implementation of creativity across all of the classrooms, despite the teachers' enthusiasm for it. In order to ensure that current and aspiring educators are able to foster creativity in their subject areas, the researcher

«ÜZLİKSİZ BİLİMLENDİRİW SISTEMASINDA ARALIQTAN OQITIVDIN INTEGRACIYASI»

atamasındaqı IV Xalıqaralıq ilimiy-teoriyalıq konferenciya

recommends professional development and teacher training focused on the creative process. Providing teachers with actionable techniques and training on the creative process would encourage creative pedagogy across all subject areas. Evidence was found that curriculum had little influence on whether creativity was fostered in the classroom. Although the lesson plans in the scientific and social studies curricula were shared between instructors at the school, the researcher still observed many opportunities for fostering creativity. Researchers recommend building teacher awareness of creativity, the creative process, and creative pedagogy, since evidence supports the claim that teachers play a substantial role in fostering creativity.

I classified articles as the atmosphere and tools which help to foster students' creative skills and the second group includes influences of teachers and additional skills to nurture students' creativity. The research findings show that a learning environment can considerably enhance students' creative skills. It also influences students' network ties, learning goal orientation, and knowledge sharing effectively which facilitate creativity potential. The findings of the research show that creative potential which is assessed by fluency is positively connected with global scores of creative activities. These scores of creative success and activities are interconnected emotional creativity and its facets. (Sordia,N &Neubaur 2019) Moreover, the positive combination of collaborative storytelling, physical activity, the field trip along with using imagination showed astonishing results when students prepared a short animated movie. Their concentration level and collaboration skills were enhanced significantly. (Collard & Looney, 2019). The research analysis revealed that enhancing ideation skills are a key to accomplished creativity training programs. Moreover, creative products or ideas come from idea generation skills; if we want to improve students' creativity we firstly should give our main attention to the developing generation process. When there is no idea generation activity, there won't be any creativity. According to the teacher's perception, students are influenced directly or indirectly by their teachers on learning, getting motivated, and developing creativity. The research analysis the importance of creativity for teachers, and the participants show a strong belief that creativity has great value in the classroom (Ryan & Hogan,2018). Moreover, the researchers identified the connection between divergent thinking, imagination, reflection, and critical thinking as crucial for promoting novelty. When a teacher controls the conversation based on his or her own preferences, it may result in students' mini-c creative ideas not being converted into little-c creative ideas. For students to be able to explore and develop their ideas there

«ÜZLİKSİZ BİLİMLENDİRİW SISTEMASINDA ARALIQTAN OQITIVDİN INTEGRACIYASI»

atamasındaqı IV Xalıqaralıq ilimiy-teoriyalıq konferenciya

is a need for fewer students per teacher and a focus on the process rather than the product of creativity

However, the study findings revealed that teachers had little understanding of creativity and the creative process. There was a lack of uniform implementation of creativity across all of the classrooms, despite the teachers' enthusiasm for it. In order to ensure that current and aspiring educators are able to foster creativity in their subject areas, the researcher recommends professional development and teacher training focused on the creative process.

Conclusion. As my research topic focuses on methods and techniques to foster secondary school children, in my study it is possible to use interesting toys and gadgets to create compelling atmosphere for children. The connection to my research topic is the importance of context. When giving theoretical knowledge to students about creativity; it is important to remove unnecessary materials from the course. Moreover, trying to improve students' divergent thinking skills by using the same method as the researcher does leads effectiveness in the forthcoming researches. Paying more attention to create appropriate environment for students and understanding different types of emotion help to implement creativity more effectively in the classroom.

Reference:

1. Collard, P. & Looney, J., (2019). Nurturing Creativity in Education. *European Journal of Education*, 49(3), pp.348-364.
2. Ryan, C., James, M. & Hogan, M., (2018). Nurturing creativity in the classroom. *The Journal of Positive Psychology*, 8(1), pp.78-83.
3. Sordia, N., Martskvishvili, K. and Neubauer, A., 2019. From Creative Potential to Creative Achievements. *Swiss Journal of Psychology*, 78(3-4), pp.115-123. Stacia Austin, Nurturing creativity: Perspectives and practices, nurturing creativity: *Louisiana Second Grade Teachers' Perspectives and Practices*. pp 1 -21.